

NOTES

Alkali Metal Complexes : Mixed Ligand Complexes of Alkali Metal Salts of Some Organic Acids with Ethylenediamine

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ETHYLENEDIAMINE (en) forms a number of stable adducts with certain alkali metals¹ and their crystal structure showed that in case of lithium, each ion is tetrahedrally surrounded by four nitrogen atoms from three ethylenediamine molecules². So it was thought worthwhile to extend the investigation by a systematic examination, and in the present work, we are reporting the synthesis of a number of stable and soluble mixed ligand complexes of ethylenediamine with alkali metal salts of some organic acids.

Experimental

The usual method of preparation of all the metal salts of organic acids was same except that for metal salts of picolinic acid. The powdered salts were taken in a flask and benzene was added to it, the salts were insoluble in benzene. This suspension of salts in benzene was heated to boiling and

ethylenediamine was added to it dropwise. The addition of ethylenediamine was continued till whole of the salt went into solution. After that the clear solution was evaporated at 110°. The heating was done very slowly and cautiously till almost whole of the liquid evaporated off. The crystals, thus obtained, were then scratched and washed with small amount of cold benzene and dried in an oven at a temperature of 100°. In the case of metal picolates, the clear solution of benzene with M.PicA and ethylenediamine, were allowed to cool when white crystals separated out. These were filtered, washed with cold benzene and dried at a temperature of 100°.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are stable in dry air. As the alkali metal complexes take up moisture and decompose due to hydrolysis, these complexes were kept in a desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂. When the system is heated, a transformation at a temperature higher than the boiling point of ethylenediamine is produced. The colour, transition or decomposition temperatures and analysis of the complexes are given in Table 1.

The solubilisation of the alkali metal salts of these organic acids in benzene by the addition of ethylenediamine clearly shows that complexes are formed in solution. Covalency in these complexes

TABLE 1—SOME PROPERTIES AND ANALYTICAL DATA

Compound	Colour	Temperature	Found(%)				Calculated(%)			
			C	H	N	M	C	H	N	M
Li8HQ.en	Yellowish brown	240-244d	62.80	5.72	19.84	—	62.56	6.64	19.91	—
Na8HQ.en	Yellow	120d	58.80	5.40	18.66	10.00	58.15	6.17	18.50	10.13
K 8HQ.en	Olive	140-160d	58.85	5.90	16.88	16.00	54.22	5.76	17.28	16.05
NaONP.en	Red	150d	43.27	5.40	18.57	11.05	43.44	5.43	19.00	10.41
K ONP.en	Orange red	120-140d	39.90	4.67	17.15	16.80	40.51	5.06	17.72	16.46
LiPicA.en	White	170d	50.80	5.88	21.90	—	50.79	6.95	22.22	—
NaPicA.en	Pale yellow	248d	46.28	5.95	19.88	11.00	46.88	5.85	20.49	11.22
LiAnth.en	Light brown	235d	52.56	8.01	19.80	—	52.43	8.25	20.39	—
NaAnth.en	Light brown	240d	49.20	7.87	18.52	10.13	48.65	7.66	18.92	10.36
LiSalA.en	Pale yellow	205-210t	52.10	6.50	18.86	—	52.94	6.97	18.73	—
NaSalA.en	Light brown	240-245d	49.60	5.71	12.42	10.32	49.09	5.91	12.73	10.45
LiSalH.en	Yellow	140-145d	57.51	6.68	14.42	—	57.45	6.91	14.89	—
NaSalH.en	Yellow	115d	53.50	6.50	13.34	11.31	52.94	6.87	13.73	11.27
K SalH.en	Brown	240d	48.81	5.95	12.10	17.52	49.09	5.91	12.73	17.73
Na1N2N.en	Green	185d	55.91	5.07	16.90	9.02	56.47	5.49	16.47	9.02
K2H3NA.en	Light brown	220-225d	54.20	5.50	9.95	13.73	54.55	5.24	9.79	13.64

d=decomposition ; t=transition.

en=ethylenediamine ; 8HQ=8-hydroxyquinoline ; ONP=o-nitrophenol ; PicA=picolinic acid ; Anth=anthranilic acid ; SalA=salicylic acid ; SalH=salicylaldehyde ; 1N2N=1-nitroso-2-naphthol ; 2H3NA=2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid.

is suggested on the basis that these are soluble in non-polar solvent benzene. That these adducts are genuine complexes and not stoichiometric mixtures is also clear from the fact that these complexes decompose at a temperature much higher than the boiling point of ethylenediamine. The complexes in absence of excess of ethylenediamine decompose in non-aqueous solvents, leaving the insoluble metal salts. As such conductivity values could not be ascertained.

An examination of the infrared spectra of alkali-metal-ethylenediamine complexes shows (Table 2)

TABLE 2—SELECTED IR ABSORPTION BANDS (cm^{-1})

Li8HQ.en	3390	3200 1610	1330 1020 810	795
KSaIH.en	3370	3200 1605sh	1320 1030 820sh	810
LiSaIA.en	3370	3180 1605	1295 1020 825	820
NaSaIA.en	3360	3200 1600sh	1320 1025 810	800sh
LiAnth.en	3380	3270 1610	1320 1028 822	800
NaAnth.en	3450 3400 3340		1040 825	820sh

sh=shoulder.

that different NH_2 vibrations are present in the complexes; though in some cases the vibrations of the acid-salts of alkali metals overlap the NH_2 vibrations. When these frequencies are compared with those obtained for Zn, Cd and Hg³, there seems no doubt, that *en* group in all these compounds has the same configuration.

The two N-H stretching vibrations appear as medium peaks between $3400\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The 3377 cm^{-1} peak of ethylenediamine remains unaffected after complexation, but the 3316 cm^{-1} peak is very much affected in the complexes. This appears at 3200 cm^{-1} with reduced intensity in the complexes thereby suggesting that there has been decrease in the bond order of N-H on complexation. The NH_2 bend vibration can be located as a single sharp peak (or shoulder) at 1605 cm^{-1} region. The ligand vibrations of the acid-salts very much interfere with the NH_2 bend vibrations. The NH_2 wag and twist appear at 1320 and 1020 cm^{-1} region as weak or medium peak.

On comparing the vibrations of NH_2 in ethylenediamine in alkali-metal salt-ethylenediamine complexes with that of 'standards'⁴ whose structures are already known, it is suggested that, because of the similarity and simpleness of the spectra, ethylenediamine has a bridging *trans*-structure.

Further to have more evidence regarding the *trans*-structure, the CH_2 rocking region $870\text{--}900\text{ cm}^{-1}$, were also looked into. In all the complexes two peaks appeared between $820\text{--}800\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which further points to *trans*-structure⁵.

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Studies on Vanadium (V)-N-*m*-Tolyl-*p*-Methoxy-Benzohydroxamic Acid Complex

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N-*m*-TOLYL-*p*-METHOXYBENZOHYDROXAMIC acid (TMBHA) has been used for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V) by solvent extraction technique¹. The present paper deals with the determination of dissociation constant of the reagent (TMBHA) from the extraction data analysis and evaluation of the stepwise stability constants of its complex with vanadium(V). The Yatsimirskii's^{2,3} and Leden's⁴ graphical extrapolation methods were applied with necessary modification⁵ to calculate the values of stepwise stability constants. The overall stability constants of the complex also have been determined by Job's⁶ and Harvey and Manning's⁷ methods.

Experimental

Reagent and solutions: A stock solution of V(V) was prepared by dissolving vanadium pentoxide (A.R.; B.D.H.) in dilute hydrochloric acid and the vanadium content was determined by standard methods⁸.

N-m-Tolyl-p-methoxybenzohydroxamic acid (TMBHA) was synthesised by known methods⁹. A fresh solution of the reagent was prepared in pure chloroform.

Apparatus: An ELICO pH meter with glass and saturated calomel electrode was employed for pH adjustments. Beckman DU2 spectrophotometer with quartz cells of 1.00 cm light path was used for all photometric measurements. All measurements were made at $30 \pm 1^\circ$.

General Procedure: An aliquot of the vanadium(V) solution was taken and to it added enough concentrated hydrochloric acid so as to make acid strength about 4.0 M. Total volume of the aqueous phase was made upto 10 ml with double distilled